

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS OF FUTURE PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: In this article, scientific-theoretical discussions are held about innovative and effective approaches to increase the professional competence of educators of future preschool educational organizations.

Key words: educator, preschool educational institution, activity, competence, innovative approach.

The Uzbek nation is among the young nations. They pay great attention to the child's education and his future. Every developing young generation is the future of tomorrow. For this reason, when we talk about education, we cannot do without stopping and paying attention to the issue of education of the perfect generation. First of all, the family and parents play a leading role in the child's upbringing, and then the preschool educational institutions and the school take the main place. A child under parental control in the family enters a preschool educational institution after reaching a certain age. There he meets children of his own age and communicates with them throughout the day. Educators of the preschool educational institution are of great importance in maintaining the balance between children and ensuring effective relations between them.

In recent years, a lot of attention has been paid to our children, who are the foundation of our future, that is, to the preschool education system. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ3261 dated September 9, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the preschool education system", No. PQ-2707 adopted on December 29, 2016 Decision of the Ministry of Preschool Education No. 3032 dated July 3, 2018 "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021" on approval of requirements", Law No. PQ-595 of December 16, 2019 "On preschool education and upbringing", Law No. PQ 4312 of May 8, 2019 "On the preschool education system until 2030 concept of development", Decree No. PF 6108 of November 6, 2020 "On measures for the development of the fields of education and science in the period of new development of Uzbekistan" and similar decisions before school served to introduce significant updates to the process of education and training in educational organizations.

Since 2018, the "First Step" curriculum based on the Korean experience has been introduced in preschool educational institutions in our country. According to the new program, trainings with children in preschool education organizations will be organized in five activity centers. This in itself shows that pedagogues working in higher educational

institutions training future specialists are required to introduce innovations in content and form into the educational process, and to introduce creativity into the educational process¹.

The management and organization of the preschool educational institution and the requirements for its employees are regulated on the basis of the law. The child's pre-school education and what competencies he/she has are defined in the "State requirements for the development of primary and pre-school children of the Republic of Uzbekistan" according to 5 areas of the child's development. These are:

- ❖ *physical development and formation of a healthy lifestyle;*
- ❖ *socio-emotional development;*
- ❖ *speech, communication, reading and writing;*
- ❖ *development of the cognitive process;*
- ❖ *creative development.*

In addition, it is permissible to list the following principles. Person-oriented education is the main principle of education and training reflected in the "First Step" State Curriculum and the Concept of Development of Pre-School Education until 2030. This pedagogical concept was developed on the basis of observing the work of educators working in preschool educational institutions, as well as experiences in various educational seminars.

Pedagogical concept primarily serves to increase pedagogical competence, and at the same time, through this concept, preschool organizations and educators will be a little motivation for working on themselves, and at the same time, it will be a guiding guide. we cry At the time of writing this concept, in order to fully apply the instructions and directions in the concept to life, I need to constantly work on myself and apply modern pedagogical technologies to my educational process for at least 2 years. It should be mentioned that in order to provide a comfortable environment for children to develop at their individual rhythm and to increase their individual potential and interest, the educator must have certain professional competencies. In order to educate a mature and mature person, it is necessary for educators to have high competencies.

Preschool education organizations should also be able to respond to innovative educational approaches. It is necessary to be able to acquaint children with the necessary information and modern medical resources. For this, it is necessary that the competence of working with information is sufficiently formed in educators. Searching for information in the world of information, being able to sort it, and providing information to children based on their age characteristics and interests is considered a very responsible task³. It is necessary to create conditions for increasing the competence of educators in using information technologies in preschool educational organizations, and for educators and pedagogues to work on themselves regularly. Another important competence is the development of the process that serves to develop the knowledge of imagery in children.

In order to develop the ability of each child to embody the surrounding environment in his imagination and language or with colored pencils and clay, the educator should help him.

¹ The importance of developing the creative competence of future educators in preschool education organizations"Saydullayeva Nargis Ilhom qizi JDPI "Maktabgacha ta'lim";

It is the task of raising teachers who understand the specific complexities of fine art and have the skills to share its subtle aspects with preschool children. The role of the educator in shaping the aesthetic abilities of children through visual activity in pre-school educational institutions is incomparable. Visual activity training is the process of application, construction and making with the help of colored pencils, colored paper, clay, plasticine. This child represents the world in his imagination and image. The main activity of preschool children is play. The issue of children's games of this age has been the focus of attention of many scientists since ancient times. At what age is the child interested in what kind of game? What games do you play the most? What kinds of games help them grow both mentally and physically? They sought answers to such questions.

In pre-school educational organizations, the educator plays the main role in organizing games for children. Meaningful and role-playing games help to develop many mental processes and personal psychological qualities of children. Consequently, children's willful qualities develop rapidly during play. So, children's games of kindergarten age have the following psychological characteristics:

- *excessive content and richness of the game theme;*
- *reflection of national feeling in children's play activities;*
- *in the manifestation of patriotic feelings during the game. The games, toys, and crafts of children of middle and senior kindergarten age are based on national customs and traditions;*
- *It is the manifestation of attention, intuition and perception, memory, thinking and speech, imagination, emotion, will, character and ability of children's mental processes during the game².*

It is the teacher's task to draw children into the game and make them interested. For this reason, it is necessary for the educator to have sufficient psychological knowledge, to be able to understand children's interests from their behavior. For this, the educator must have pedagogic skills. Skill is the result of deep knowledge and research. It is necessary to develop the competence of teachers to acquire knowledge and work on themselves. The game helps the child to understand life. In order for them to help the child, in addition to physical activity, to grow mentally and spiritually, it is appropriate for the educator to be able to choose the necessary type of game and perform it together with the children.

The game is very important in the mental development of a child. The game not only improves cognitive processes, but also has a positive effect on the child's behavior. According to Z.V.Manuyleko, who studied the psychological problem related to the development of self-control skills in children of kindergarten age, it is possible to acquire behavioral skills earlier and easier in a game than in a goal-oriented training³.

In addition to these, the educators of the preschool educational organization should have the following competencies and develop them continuously. Innovative approaches that every teacher should have:

- ❖ Social approach - acquiring skills and abilities to be active in social issues.

² S.X. Jalilova, S.M. Aripova., «Psychology of preschool children». «Philosophers» T., 2017 y.

³ P.Yusupova. «Pedagogy of preschool education». «Oqituvchi» T., 1993 y

- ❖ Special approach - preparation for organization of professional-pedagogical activities, solving professional problems, rational assessment of activity results. This type of competence is divided into several types:
- ❖ Psychological approach - the ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, to create an effective process of communication with children, to get along with them.
- ❖ Methodical approach - methodically correct organization of the process, rational choice of forms of educational activities, ability to use methods and tools appropriately.
- ❖ Creative and communicative approach - the ability to demonstrate one's creativity and communicate effectively with all participants in the education and training process, to have a positive influence on them and to be able to listen.

As a conclusion, it can be said that every person participating in the process of education and upbringing must approach his work responsibly, constantly work on himself and be able to meet the requirements of modern education. This is the demand of today. Therefore, it is the demand of the time to pay attention to education based on an innovative approach.

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